

The Impact of Gestational Diabetes on Babies: A Closer Look

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Abstract:- Diabetes is a chronic-condition, that necessitates ongoing medical care to patient, patient education, and support for self-management in order to avoid acute complications and decrease long-term repercussions. Therefore, the epidemic of Diabetic mellitus (DM) is followed by a burden of diabetes-related vascular disease. In particular, type 2 diabetes is an epidemic that requires global attention as cardiovascular risk. As the population ages, persons with diabetes are becoming more prevalent. This is partly due to increased obesity and physical inactivity. Globally, both hyperglycemia during pregnancy and obesity in women of childbearing age have reached epidemic proportions (1:2). Untreated diabetic pregnancies are associated with high perinatal mortality and morbidity. However, screening, prenatal fetal monitoring, and insulin therapy significantly reduced this value. This article reviews the definition, risk factors, etiology, screening and treatment, maternal and fetal complications, side effects, and prevention of diabetes during pregnancy.

Keywords:- Diabetic mellitus, Gestational diabetes, Treatment, Complications, Diagnostic criteria.

I. INTRODUCTION

High blood glucose (sugar) levels are a defining characteristic of diabetes, a chronic medical illness. It happens when the body is either unable to use the insulin it generates or does not make enough of it. The pancreas secretes insulin, a hormone that controls how glucose is metabolised and facilitates its entry into cells where it can be used as fuel. Glucose builds up in the blood without enough insulin or with improper insulin activity, which can cause a number of health issues. Diabetes can cause blood sugar levels to rise if it is not continuously and carefully managed, which raises the chance of serious side effects like heart attack and stroke. The number of people with diabetes is expected to increase by 31%, from 1.18 million in 1998 to 1.51 million in 2023 primarily as a result of the ageing population. According to the United States Diabetes Market Report 2023, there will be a 3.26% annual increase in the number of people with diabetes, increasing the need for insulin. An estimated 77 million adults in India over the age of 18 have type 2 diabetes, and close to 25 million are prediabetes (with an increased risk of getting diabetes soon). If not identified and treated promptly, more than 50% of people will have health issues due to their diabetes. Adults with diabetes are two to three times more likely to experience a heart attack or stroke. Neuropathy (nerve damage) in the feet raises the risk of foot ulcers, infection, and ultimately the requirement for limb amputation when combined with decreased blood flow.

Generally there are three types of diabetes, namely: type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes, gestational diabetes.

- **Type 1 diabetes:** Type 1 diabetic mellitus, also referred to as insulin-dependent diabetes or juvenile diabetes, typically manifests throughout childhood or adolescence. It happens when the immune system unintentionally targets and kills the pancreatic cells that make insulin. People with type 1 diabetes need lifelong insulin therapy since their bodies are unable to manufacture insulin as a result.
- **Type 2 diabetes:** Type 2 diabetes makes up 90% to 95% of all cases of the disease, making it the most prevalent type. As obesity rates rise, more children and adolescents are being diagnosed with it even though it typically develops in adults. When the body develops a tolerance to the effects of insulin and the pancreas is unable to generate enough insulin to overcome the resistance, type 2 diabetes is greatly influenced by the lifestyle elements like weight, a sedentary lifestyle, a poor diet, and genetics.
- **Gestational diabetes:** Pregnant women are affected by gestational diabetes are affected. Insulin resistance is caused by hormonal changes that occur during pregnancy. After giving birth, the majority of women with gestational diabetes see their blood sugar levels return to normal. But they have a higher chance of getting type 2 diabetes in later life.
- **Symptoms includes** Frequent urination, excessive thirst, unexplained weight loss, increased hunger, exhaustion, sluggish wound healing, recurring infections, and blurred eyesight are typical signs of diabetes. However, some people may not exhibit any symptoms at all, particularly in the early stages of type 2 diabetes. Diabetes can cause a number of problems that can damage numerous organ systems if it is untreated or inadequately controlled. several of the long-term complications like cardiovascular diseases, diabetic nephropathy, diabetic retinopathy, and diabetic neuropathy.

II. WHAT IS GESTATIONAL DIABETES?

A form of diabetes known as gestational diabetes affects pregnant women. It is characterised by instances of elevated blood sugar that occur or are first noticed during gestation. This illness is a reasonably typical pregnancy problem because it affects 2 to 10 pregnant women on average. Pregnancy-related diabetes causes Insulin resistance is a disease that develops as a result of hormonal changes that occur during pregnancy and can make cells more resistant to insulin. The hormone insulin, which is made by the pancreas, aids in controlling blood sugar levels. The pancreas may not be able to produce sufficient amount of enough insulin in some women, resulting in Gestational diabetes, to overcome this resistance. Generally speaking, a number of hormones help to regulate blood sugar levels. However, because of the

hormonal changes that occur during pregnancy, it efficiently reusing blood sugar is more difficult for the body. This causes a spike in blood sugar. Insulin resistance develops as pregnancy goes on as the levels of many hormones, including cortisol and oestrogen, rise. The 26th to the 33rd week of Threaten is when these hormones reach their peak influence. For instance, cortisol has a very potent diabetogenic effect. A gravid diabetes diagnosis increases the risk of perinatal hypertension. Additionally, it may raise the risk of having a large baby that requires a caesarean surgery (C-section). Symptoms Pregnant women must endure screening procedures in order to detect gestational diabetes because it typically doesn't cause obvious symptoms. Typically, these tests are performed between 24 and 28 weeks of gestation. Maternal age >35 years, obesity (BMI 30 kg/m²), familial history of diabetes, history of GDM, and history of Macrosomia (neonatal weight 4000 g) are the main risk factors that affect diagnosis of gestational diabetes.

The pathogenesis and underlying mechanisms of gestational diabetes involve a combination of hormonal, metabolic, and placental factors.

• **Insulin Resistance:** At the time of pregnancy, the placenta produces a hormones that helps maintain the pregnancy. Progesterone and (HPL) Human placental lactogen hormones can interfere with the action of insulin and cause insulin resistance. Insulin resistance reduces the effectiveness of insulin to move glucose from the bloodstream to cells, causing elevated blood sugar levels.

- **Increased insulin production:** In response to insulin resistance, the pancreas produces more insulin to compensate for its reduced effectiveness. This compensatory increase in insulin production is aimed at maintaining normal blood sugar levels. However, in some cases, the pancreas cannot produce enough insulin to overcome insulin resistance, which can lead to gestational diabetes.
- **Beta cell dysfunction:** During pregnancy, beta cells of the pancreas which produces insulin can also malfunction, contributing to the development of gestational diabetes. This dysfunction may be due to several factors, including genetic predisposition and metabolic stress caused by pregnancy-related hormonal changes.
- **Glucose dysregulation:** In gestational diabetes, the body's ability to regulate glucose levels is impaired. This is primarily due to insulin resistance, in which glucose is not efficiently transported into cells for energy production. This keeps your blood sugar elevated.
- **Placental factors:** The placenta plays an important role in gestational diabetes. It produces hormones that can interfere with the action of insulin and can lead to insulin resistance. In addition, the placenta may release other substances such as adipokines and inflammatory cytokines that further cause metabolic disturbances and insulin resistance. Other factors such as genetic and environmental factors are also underlying causes of gestational diabetes.

Fig. 1: Consequences on the progeny caused by diabetes mellitus exposure during pregnancy

A. Threat factors:

Threat factors of Gestational diabetes are

- Being fat or fat
- Not being physically active
- Having prediabetes
- Having had gravid diabetes during a former gestation
- Having polycystic ovary pattern
- Having an immediate family member with diabetes
- Having a kid who weighs more than 9 pounds (4.1 kilogrammes) and has complications Diabetes during pregnancy may also make preeclampsia and high blood pressure more likely. The risk of a dangerous pregnancy complication that results in high blood pressure and other symptoms that could endanger both your life and the life of your unborn child increases if you have gestational diabetes.
- Experiencing difficulties during a C-section. The risk of acquiring type 2 diabetes as you age is higher for people with gestational diabetes.
- The effect of gestational diabetes on a baby can have various goods on the baby during gestation and after birth. When blood sugar situations are Uncontrolled or constantly high, it can pose Detect to the developing foetus. Babies of diabetic mothers are prone to perinatal suffocation and delivery traumas, mothers are more likely to have discomfort neonatal unfavourable concerns, such as metabolic and hematologic illnesses, respiratory distress, heart diseases, and neurologic impairment.

- Macrosomia inadequately controlled Gestational diabetes can lead to inordinate growth of the baby.
- Hypoglycaemia Babies born to mothers With Gestational diabetes may have Uncontrolled low blood sugar situations (hypoglycemia) shortly after birth. This occurs because the baby’s pancreas has been producing redundant insulin to manage the advanced glucose situations in the womb.
- Respiratory Distress pattern (RDS) Babies born to maters, With condition of Gestational diabetes may be at an advanced threat of developing respiratory Distress patterns. RDS is a condition in which the baby’s lungs aren’t completely developed, leading to breathing difficulties.
- Jaundice Babies of mothers With Gestational diabetes may have an advanced threat of developing hostility. Hostility occurs when there’s a redundant buildup of bilirubin, a yellow color produced during the breakdown of red blood cells. It can Gestational yellowing of the skin and eyes.
- Increased threat of Obesity and type 2 diabetes, infants born to mothers With gestational diabetes are more likely to develop Obesity and type 2 diabetes latterly in life. Exposure to high blood sugar situations in the womb can impact the baby’s metabolism and increase the threat of developing these conditions in the majority.

Fig. 2: Prenatal problems and maternal risk factors related to gestational diabetes mellitus.

B. Glucose Monitoring:

Monitoring of your blood sugar levels is essential in control of gestational diabetes. Keeping track of blood sugar levels and making the necessary modifications to maintain stable glucose levels during pregnancy aids pregnant women with gestational diabetes.

- **Self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG):** The most popular approach to glucose monitoring in gestational diabetes is self monitoring of blood glucose. It entails measuring blood sugar levels at home using a glucose meter. Typically, healthcare professionals advise testing at specified times, such as postprandial (after-meal) blood sugar levels and fasting blood-Sugar levels in the morning.
- **Glucose objectives:** For pregnant women with gestational diabetes, healthcare professionals will set particular blood sugar targets. These goals could change depending on things including postprandial testing, fasting, individual circumstances, and medical recommendations.

- **Documenting and tracking:** It's important to document blood sugar readings. Both the pregnant woman and the healthcare professionals can use this data to track patterns, spot trends, and modify the treatment plan as necessary.
- **Glucose monitoring tools:** Using a little blood sample taken from a finger prick with a lancet, glucose meters, which are portable devices, detect blood sugar levels. These meters offer speedy findings, and several versions have attributes like memory storage, reading averaging, and data connectivity for simple tracking.
- **Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM):** In some circumstances, healthcare professionals may advise pregnant women suffering from gestational diabetes have to use continuous- glucose monitoring (CGM). Wearing a sensor that continuously monitors the amount of glucose in the interstitial fluid is a need for CGM systems. Real-time glucose readings and trends are provided by the sensor via data transmission to a receiver or smartphone. The use of CGM devices can assist pinpoint areas where glucose control could be improved by providing useful information regarding glucose trends, including high and low glucose incidents.

Guideline	Fasting glucose (mg/dL)	1-Hr postprandial Glucose (mg/dL)	2-Hr postprandial glucose (mg/dL)
ACOG	95	140	120
ADA	95	140	120
Endocrine Society	95	140	120
NICE	95	140	115

Fig. 3: Recommend glycemic targets for patients with Pregational diabetes

C. Gestational Diabetes Treatment

There are many things you can do to control your gestational diabetes, such as: routinely checking your blood sugar levels to ensure they remain within a healthy range.

Starting a pregnancy at a healthy weight is advised. You might be expecting healthier pregnancy if you lose extra weight before getting pregnant. Focus on making long-lasting dietary changes that will help you while you're expecting, such eating healthful meals in the right amounts at the right times. Follow the diet your doctor or nutritionist has recommended.

Making a move: Regular moderate-intensity activity, like as brisk walking, lowers blood sugar and improves insulin sensitivity, which lowers the amount of insulin your body needs.

D. Pharmacological therapy includes:

- **Insulin:** Therapeutic intervention with insulin should be explored if diet and exercise are insufficient to maintain euglycemia. The identification of women who will need insulin therapy depends on regular blood sugar monitoring. The ADA's most recent recommendations include routinely checking both fasting and after eating glucose levels every 1-2 weeks. As an alternative, measuring SMBG can be a helpful way to evaluate glycemic control.
- **Oral hypoglycaemic agents (OHAs):** Oral hypoglycemia medicines are rarely used to treat diabetes in women. At early times sulfonylureas, particularly chlorpropamide, and tolbutamide, are contraindicated during pregnancy, because they may cause hypoglycemia and other fetal abnormalities. Since glibenclamide does not cross the placenta, it may be used to treat GDM.

III. CONCLUSION

In summary, A persistent metabolic disorder called diabetes is characterised by high-blood sugar levels. It is a major worldwide health burden because to its rising prevalence and related problems. Type 1, Type 2, Pregnancy Type, Special Type, etc. are the different categories. Each variety has unique pathophysiological pathways, necessitating individual treatment plans. Preventing both short-term and long-term consequences such cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, nephropathy, and retinopathy requires maintaining blood glucose levels within target limits. A complex strategy that incorporates lifestyle modifications, pharmaceutical management, routine blood glucose testing, and thorough management of related comorbidities is necessary for effective management of diabetes. Patient support and education are crucial in enabling people to successfully manage their condition on their own. By promoting early detection, effective therapy, and continuous support, healthcare professionals can enhance results and people's health.

REFERENCES

- [1.] American Diabetes Association. Gestational Diabetes. *Diabetes Care*. 1999;22: S74–78. [Google Scholar]
- [2.] American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists. (2018). Practice Bulletin No. 190: Gestational Diabetes Mellitus. *Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 131(2), e49-e64. DOI: 10.1097/AOG.0000000000002501
- [3.] International Diabetes Federation. (2019). *IDF Diabetes Atlas, 9th edition*. Brussels, Belgium: International Diabetes Federation.
- [4.] American Diabetes Association. (2019). Management of diabetes in pregnancy: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2019. *Diabetes Care*, 42(Supplement 1), S165-S172. DOI: 10.2337/dc19-S015
- [5.] <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3406210/>
- [6.] Asemi, Z.; Samimi, M.; Tabassi, Z.; Esmailzadeh, A. The effect of DASH diet on pregnancy outcomes in gestational diabetes: A randomized controlled clinical trial. *Eur. J. Clin. Nutr.* 2014, 68, 490–495. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [7.] <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-0383/11/19/5736>
- [8.] A review article- gestational diabetes mellitus: Akhalya K, Sreelatha S, Rajeshwari, et al. A review article- gestational diabetes mellitus. *Endocrinol Metab Int J.* 2019;7(1):26-39. DOI: 10.15406/emij.2019.07.00238
- [9.] “Consensus statement on self-monitoring in diabetes: Institute of Health Economics, Alberta, Canada, November 14-16, 2006”, *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 2007.